
**THE VALUE OF USING GAME EXERCISES WHEN TEACHING THE
CHAPTER "ORGANS AND ORGAN SYSTEMS" IN THE 7TH GRADE OF
BIOLOGY"**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012437>

Ravshanova Mukhabbat

*Department of Biology Educations, Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan*

Shomurodov Normurod

*Department of Biology Educations, Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan*

Abstract.

This article shows the importance of using game exercises in the example of teaching the chapter "Organs and Organ Systems" in the 7th grade of the subject of biology to increase students' interest in learning and thereby develop their independent learning skills.

Keywords.

game exercises, training, upbringing, memory, skills, independent acquisition of knowledge, biology, botany, zoology.

Introduction

7th grade in biology, the diversity of living organisms, the molecular and cellular level of life, organs and organ systems, coordination and self-control, nutrition, respiration, transport of substances in living organisms, subtraction, movement, growth and development, type, population, ecosystem, biosphere, and other topics are given to students. Today, it is a difficult task to increase students' interest in learning with simple lessons. The reason is that today's youth are well aware of modern technology and scientific innovations. From this point of view, it is necessary to use special methods in classes to increase their interest in learning. Taking into account the age characteristics of students in the grade 7 lessons, ensures easy assimilation of the learned knowledge, and students' skills of cooperation, and independent learning forms

The main goal of game exercises is to increase the efficiency of independent learning by increasing the interest of students in studying the basics of science;

Literature analysis and methods:

In 2011, "Tafakkur" Publishing House published a book by J.O. Tolipova, M.T. The methodical manual for 6th grade teachers "Botany lessons" published by Umaraliyeva provides information on the types of game exercises, methods of their use in the classroom. [1].

2011 A.G. In the textbook "Использование игр на уроках биологии»:, published by Kozlenko, the use of game exercises in biology lessons, their types, negative and positive aspects of using game exercises, their impact on the effectiveness of education and training. information about rni has been given. [6].

In 1996 Pidkasistyy P.I., Khaydarov J.S. The textbook "Technology of Games in Training and Development", published by the author, provides information on the importance of the use of game exercises in the educational process in the effectiveness of students' learning. [2].

Leslie Ray's 2003 handbook, "Developing Navigation Skills" discusses several game exercises and their use and types in the classroom. [3].

2022, in an article published by Muhabbat R. and Normurod S., the importance of using game exercises in teaching students in biology classes was also discussed. [4].

In an article published in 2022 by Muhabbat R. and Ruhsora R., they provided information on the importance of using energy exercises to increase the effectiveness of learning in biology classes [5].

In school biology, observation, questionnaires, tests, and comparisons were used to determine the effectiveness of lessons learned through games and assignments.

Discussion:

In the course of the game, students perform the given tasks not as an obligation, but according to their desire and interest. Based on the game, the pupils will increase their interest in learning science as they enrich the qualities of inquisitiveness through the feeling of striving for victory. According to the sphere of influence, games are divided into several groups: games that develop attention, imagination, memory, and logical and independent thinking skills. Games that develop imagination and memory, logical and independent thinking skills in biology lessons include "Weave a fairy tale", "Remember and Write", "Who is More", "Find the Puzzle", "Collect the Cubes" ", "Travel", "Illustrate without objects" (based on facial expressions and gestures) can be cited.

In the example of teaching the chapter "Organs and organ systems" in the subject of biology, the use of games gives the expected effect.

The use of the game "Collect the Cubess" in the topics included in the chapter "Organs and organ systems" develops students' independent learning skills.

For example, "Generative organs of plants. "Collect the cubes" game can be used on the "Flower" theme. 6 cubes with pictures of plants belonging to simple or complex inflorescences and 6 types of inflorescences are prepared for students. According to the suggestion of the teacher, one of the students goes to the blackboard and chooses one of the cards with the type (names) of flowers. They find pictures of plants related to flowers on the card, collect the cubes and fill in the following table:

Table 1

Taypes of flowers	The name of the plants
Shingle	
Spike	
An umbbrella	
Sheild	
Cope	
Shopping cart	

Types of flowers The name of plants. Shingle Spike An umbrella Shield So Shopping cart There are games that help children to concentrate and pay attention to the lesson. The use of such game exercises to increase students' attention to the lesson serves to further increase the effectiveness of education. Examples of such games are "Find the mistake in the table", "Fictitious story", "Fix the mistake", "Find it in 5 tries". Although the games look easy, light, carefree, they require students to spend a lot of effort, to use aspects such as intelligence, patience, and independence.

"Top in 5 attempts" game can be used in biology classes. For example, when using the topic "Fruit", cards with the names of several fruits or pictures are placed on the study table. A student leaves the class. The rest of the students choose the name of one fruit. When the student who left the class returns, he starts asking his classmates questions about the selected fruit. The rest will answer only "yes" or "no". The questions should be related to the morphological signs and specific characteristics of the fruit given in the textbook. The participant of the game has the right to ask only 5 questions.

For example, this game "Generative organs of plants. When playing this game on the theme of "Flower", cards with pictures of various plants are given on the table.

The student will have to find the selected plant type in 5 attempts. it is possible to know to what extent the student mastered the task through the solved questions and his answer. At the end of each game, there must be a conclusion. The teacher should clarify the terms of the game, manage the whole process, make a conclusion, and determine the winners of the game. At the end of the game, it is important to reward each participant. It is necessary to use encouraging words such as "the best", "the most agile", "sharp-minded", "intelligent", and "wise".

Outcome:

Games have a special importance not only in teaching students but also in having a positive effect on their education. To determine the effectiveness of lessons in the biological sciences using game exercises, the lessons were conducted in two different ways in the "experimental" and "control" classes, which were separated from 7 grades of the school. Biology lessons in experimental classes were based on game exercises. In the control classes, the lessons were conducted as usual without game exercises.

At the end of the experimental classes, tests are conducted in the "control" and "experimental" classes. Both comparable classes were given test questions of the same content. The number of questions asked to students was 20, and 40 minutes were allotted for work.

The results obtained in the two selected experimental and control classes were as follows:

Table 2

s/n	Experience	Control	Experience	Control
Seperated classes	7-A class	7- B class	7-v class	7-G class
Number of students	28	28	25	25
5 marks	15	10	9	6
4 marks	10	12	12	10
3 marks	3	6	3	7
2 marks	-	-	1	2
The general result	4,4	4,1	4,2	3,8

Conclusion

Conducting biology lessons through the use of games increases students' attention and interest in science, in-depth understanding of physiological processes

in living organisms, retention of information through games, formation of high moral qualities, and independent learning. is of special importance in increasing interest.

Various game exercises and assignments used in the experimental class increased the students' attention to the lesson and allowed them to deepen their understanding of the topic. Although the control questions were included in a number of topics, they had a positive effect on the memory of the topic.

In conclusion, the use of game exercises in the lessons, paying attention to the content of the topic, the age, physiological characteristics and interests of students, has a positive effect on the acquisition of in-depth knowledge of biology.

REFERENCES:

1. J.O. Tolipova, M.T. Umaraliyeva "Botany lessons" (methodical manual for 6th grade teachers) Thought. T.2011y (pages 266-267)
2. Pidkasistyy P.I., Khaidarov J.S. "Technology of games in training and development: uchebnoe posobie". - M.6 MPU, Ros. ped. agency. 1996. - (269 p.)
3. Leslie Ray "Development of training skills" Publishing House: "Peter" 2003 (pages 20-27)
4. Mukhabbat, R., & Normurod, S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF USING GAME EXERCISES IN BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS'LEARNING SKILLS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(4), 1436-1440.
5. Muhabbat, R., & Ruhsora, R. (2022). Education in biology classes-the importance of using energy effects to increase the efficiency of education. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 623-626.
6. А.Г. Козленко «Использование игр на уроках биологии»: лекции 1-4. - М.: Педагогический университет «Первое сентября», 2011. - 72 с. Учебно-методическое пособие